

“THE SCIENTIFIC IDEAS AND THOUGHTS ABOUT CRIME PREVENTION IN THE HISTOTICAL LITERATURES OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The relevance of the topic of this article is the content and specific features of the ideas and thoughts of crime prevention in the works of Uzbek thinkers and statesmen, the theoretical and conceptual foundations of the ideas and thoughts of crime prevention in the works of Uzbek thinkers and statesmen, as well as , the significance of the doctrines of the ideas and thoughts of crime prevention in the works of Uzbek thinkers and statesmen and their place today. We are witnessing that the basis of the reforms implemented in our country is obtaining the consent of our people, preserving their peace, protecting their rights and interests, strengthening their confidence in the internal affairs bodies, and a number of such priority issues.

Key words: theoretical ideas of crime prevention ideas and opinions in the works of Uzbek thinkers and statesmen, importance of teachings on ideas and opinions, priority issues.

"The new Uzbekistan will become a prosperous and prosperous country in all respects, with a strong potential, a decent reputation in the world arena. I not only believe in this, but I am always ready to mobilize my knowledge, experience, and energy in this way." I invite all our compatriots to be in such a great line - among the creators of New Uzbekistan. I think that such reforms, carried out with the spirit of humanity, are based on the profoundly meaningful words of our great grandfather Alisher Navoi, that making one sad person happy is equal to beautifying the Kaaba, kindness, generosity and It is in every way harmonious and harmonious with the dreams and aspirations of our people, who always appreciate and glorify virtues such as nobility. "We are trying to strengthen spiritual and educational work in new conditions. This approach is a solid foundation for our current and future development. In this sense, building New Uzbekistan means to continue our path of independent national development at a new stage by further studying our recent and distant history, unique and unique cultural assets, relying on them. In recent years, our people are well aware of the work we are doing in the cultural and humanitarian direction - the development of culture, cinema, dance and fine arts, literature and reading. When each young generation acquires the political, legal, and moral culture of society, it relies on the socio-political experiences of previous generations and transfers them from its consciousness, takes the good ones and applies them in its activities, thereby improving its own culture. In order to establish a legal, political and moral culture in young people, the ideology of national independence should be instilled in their worldviews and thinking in harmony with universal values and national values. Working with young people is difficult, but if they are not controlled, bad behavior will bring down the city. The ruler should study the mental state of people and society to such an extent

that "in what state of the soul people can do virtuous deeds, how to eliminate the shortcomings and vices of the city dwellers, by what artistic ways can good qualities be formed in the hearts of the city dwellers it should be clear what these qualities are and what tools can be used to preserve them". The great thinker Alisher Navoi, writing about Sufism and famous Sufi scholars, said about Yassavi: "His authority is high and famous, his merits are great and infamous. He said, "Murid and companion are incomparable and under the will and sincerity of the king." This idea refers to the time when Yassavi returned to Yassi and became famous as a murshid who founded a new sect. Sufism, which developed in Central Asia in the 11th century, was not only a religious doctrine, but also a direction of significant social importance and a collection of unique educational and educational ideas. In Sufism, the traditions of teacher and disciple are strictly adhered to, and important attention is paid to the formation of free-thinking and human qualities. These aspects are also clearly visible in the work of Ahmed Yassavi. Homeland, human expressed in Yassavi's wisdom Ethical-philosophical ideas about perfection, faith, religion, not giving in to lust, and compassion are valuable values in the education of today's youth, and they are a great contribution to our national pedagogy. Ahmed Yassavi's works are aimed at instilling the ideas of Sufism into the minds of the masses. Abdurauf Fitrat said that Yassavi's "path in literature is the narrow path of our simple folk poets. His wisdom is equal in weight, rhyme, and style to poems called folk literature." As mentioned above, in the heritage of Ahmed Yassavi, his collection of poems called "Hikmat" occupies a special place. This collection of poems is known in the natural environment as "Devoni Hikmat". Also, his pedagogical views were reflected in the work "Rasail" ("Triplets"). All the beliefs of the Yassaviya order are described in detail in the main work of Ahmed Yassavi, Hikmat. The main historical sources illuminating the life and work of Amir Temur, who was an excellent example of Turkish-language poetry in the 12th century and had a great influence on Turkish literature in later periods, are incredibly numerous and diverse, and this is his name in world history. It shows that the role is incomparable and extremely popular. Amir Temur, the Timurid state, and the scientific analysis of the research conducted abroad and in our Republic, devoted to the issues of its establishment, are covered in the books of a number of our scientists. "Tuzuklari Temur" has been interesting to the scientific community for 600 years. "In the 20s of the 13th century, as a result of the Mongol rulers taking possession of Central Asia, our science and culture were restored by the intelligence of Abu Nasr Farabi, Musa Khorezmi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ahmad Yugnaki, Mahmud Koshgari, etc. its rocks began to crumble, and Islam, which was considered the dominant ideology, lost its status. Because Movarounnahrni The main historical sources covering the life and activities of Amir Temur are incredibly numerous and diverse, which indicates that his name, his role in world history is incomparable and he is extremely popular. Amir Temur, the Timurid state, and the scientific analysis of the research conducted abroad and in our Republic, devoted to the issues of its establishment, are covered in the books of a number of our scientists. "Tuzuklari Temur" has been interesting to the scientific community for 600 years. "In the 20s of the 13th century, as a result of the Mongol rulers taking possession of Central Asia, our science and culture were restored by the intelligence of Abu Nasr Farabi, Musa Khorezmi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ahmad Yugnaki, Mahmud Koshgari, etc. its rocks began to crumble, and Islam, which was considered the dominant ideology, lost its status. As part of the prevention of crimes, it is necessary to organize legal

propaganda among the population, to determine the causes of crimes and the conditions that make them possible, to eliminate them, and to implement preventive measures in completely new directions in this regard. shows.

In the course of reforms, measures aimed at improving the crime prevention system, further improving the material and technical supply, and further increasing the efficiency of its activities are being implemented. The aim of these works is to ensure the rule of law in society, to protect the rights and freedoms of citizens.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev: "Ensuring the rule of law in the society is the main guarantee of achieving the effectiveness of all the theologies implemented, raising the standard of living of the population, ensuring peace, harmony and a stable situation in the country." He pointed out that ensuring peace and tranquility in the country is one of the urgent tasks of today. The following serious shortcomings and problems have accumulated in the implementation of preventive measures by prevention inspectors:

- in most cases, crime prevention is assessed as the task of law enforcement bodies only, and as a result, local government bodies, other state organizations, as well as economic management bodies do not pay due attention;

- the work forms and methods of the state bodies implementing crime prevention do not fully meet today's requirements, the use of information and communication technologies in this activity is not sufficiently established;

- the increasing number of crimes and offenses committed today among young people and minors, as well as within the framework of family life, determining the reasons and conditions for the systematic commission of offenses in this direction, and measures to eliminate them such as the fact that the development efficiency does not exist, that the work in this regard did not give the expected results. The prevention inspector is required to implement the following measures to more effectively organize the prevention of violations:

- in order to form and improve the legal culture of the population, to appoint employees with organizational and initiative skills, legal and pedagogical-psychological knowledge, high legal culture, and good relations with citizens to the position of senior inspectors of base prevention;

- to put an end to the existing disunity in the cooperation of other entities working together with the prevention inspectors of the base on the formation and improvement of the legal literacy of the population;

- It is necessary to organize our activities with the understanding that prevention of crimes in our country is our main goal, not to allow them to be committed or create conditions for them to be committed. taking into account that we need to be broad in our practice.

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